

FLOTANT concept: floater design, integrated modelling & global performance

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Abstract. This paper presents the final design of the FLOTANT concept developed within the framework of a Cooperation Research Project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme. The FLOTANT concept is a hybrid concrete-plastic barge-type floating offshore substructure holding a 12MW wind turbine; buoyancy is achieved using plastic material (foam) fitted within the floater substructure. The paper describes the FLOTANT project innovations and presents the principal dimensions of the floating wind turbine system. The floating system has been developed to fulfil strict requirements at two different locations: Gran Canarias (GC) and West of Barra (WoB) sites. Therefore, two different mooring solutions including innovative elastomers to reduce peak loads are presented. The floating system's intact and damaged static stability is checked along with the hydrostatic and hydrodynamic properties, showing the low-cost barge-type system's feasibility. To ensure the desired behaviour of the floating system, a relevant subset of design load cases (DLCs) based on international standard requirements have been simulated checking the global performance of floater and moorings. Fully coupled hydro-servo-aero-elastic simulations have been performed to consider the wind and wave loading, the aerodynamic response of the rotor, the hydrodynamic response and structural dynamics of the turbine-floater-mooring assembly, and the control system actions. A summary of the results of the last design loop within the FLOTANT project is presented.

1. Introduction

The FLOTANT project is developing an innovative, integrated, FOWT solution, optimised for deep waters and holding a 12MW wind turbine generator. The project is framed into a Cooperation Research Project funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

The concept developed by the consortia is a hybrid concrete-plastic barge-type floating offshore substructure with a heave plate, an active ballast system, and the singularity of getting floatability by using plastic foam material fitted within the floater substructure. The concept has evolved from the beginning of the project. Initially, a hybrid spar buoy concept was considered; however, by the end of the first loop of design [1] the development was close to the actual design and the barge-type was finally developed on the basis of a cost reduction associated with the innovative construction, installation, and operations and maintenance strategies linked with such a floater type. The final design presented below includes an innovative mooring system using high-performance polymers to reduce both weight and peak loads. Another remarkable difference between the two loops of design is the inner structure of the floater. Initially, the concept received the buoyancy from plastic inflated bags fitted into the floater whereas now, the plastic bags are substituted by blocks of extruded polystyrene foam material (XPS) filling the void spaces within the floater substructure. The concept also includes a novel design regarding the power export system based on long self-life and low-weight dynamic cables. The project also includes interesting features in the field of sensing and monitoring of both structures and cables and the evaluation of the techno-economic, environmental, social, and socio-economic impacts associated with the development of a commercial wind farm using the FLOTANT concept.

The FLOTANT technology aims to achieve an overall 60% reduction in CAPEX and 55% in OPEX allowing a competitive LCoE in the range of 85-95 €/MWh by 2030 [2].

2. Sites

The FLOTANT platform has been designed for two different locations [3]. The first of them is considered to represent the ideal conditions for commissioning a floating concept based on a barge-type floater, i.e., an area with very constant winds and low extreme wind speeds. The selected location is off the southeast coast of Gran Canaria (GC) island (Figure 1a), in the Canary Islands, Spain. The exact location and the principal site characteristics are provided in Table 1.

The second site selected to study the behaviour of the FLOTANT concept is located 19 km West of Barra (WoB) Island (Figure 1b), Scotland. This site is considered a high energy environment and was identified by a previous project funded by the European Commission under the Horizon 2020 programme as a potential area for the development of deep-water floating technology. The principal characteristics and accurate site location are also provided in Table 1.

Figure 1 GC (a) and WoB (b) site's location

Table 1 GC and WoB sites characteristics

Item	Unit	GC	WoB
Water Depth	m	250.00	100.00
V_{50}	m/s	28.00	50.00
H_{S50}	m	5.11	15.60
T_{p50}	s	12.00	15.20
Seabed type	-	Sand	Basalt

3. Wind turbine

The wind turbine developed for the FLOTANT project is the INS12MW generic wind turbine (GWT) resulting from the upscaling exercise of the DTU10MW reference wind turbine (RWT), an existing public aeroelastic model designed by the DTU as part of the Light Rotor project [4]. Table 2 presents the main properties of INS12MW GWT [5]. Figure 2 depicts thrust and the steady-state behaviour of the INS12MW GWT.

Table 2 Principal wind turbine characteristics

Item	Unit	INS12MW GWT
Output power	MW	12.00
Rotor diameter	m	195.40
Hub diameter	m	6.13
Hub height above sea level	m	119.70
Tower mass	t	782.00
Nacelle mass including rotor (RNA)	t	836.00
Distance from Tower Top to Hub Height	m	3.01
Cut-in wind speed	m/s	4.00
Rated wind speed	m/s	11.40
Cut-out wind speed	m/s	25.00
Cut-in rotor speed	rpm	3.50
Rated rotor speed	rpm	8.76

Figure 2 Main steady-state parameters (a) and thrust force (b) versus wind speed

3.1. Aeroelastic modelling

Using OpenFAST [6], the open-source glue code developed by NREL, an aeroelastic model of the INS12MW wind turbine has been developed. OpenFAST uses the results of several pre-processors (e.g., IECWind, TurbSim among others), and combines them within several simulations (e.g., ElastoDyn, InflowWind, AeroDyn, ServoDyn among others) to calculate the coupled dynamic response of the wind turbine.

The pre-processors are tools designed for helping to create aero-elastic models. They produce relevant information needed to feed the simulation tools. IECWind is a utility program used to create wind files that model the extreme conditions outlined in [7] for AeroDyn-based programs. TurbSim is a stochastic, full-field, turbulent-wind simulator using a statistical model to generate time series of three-component wind speed for AeroDyn-based codes such as OpenFAST.

As stated before, OpenFAST couples results from different simulations. ElastoDyn is a dynamic structural model able to represent the rotor, drivetrain, nacelle, tower, and platform. It computes displacement, velocities, accelerations, and reactions from the acting loads taking into account the controller and the substructure reactions. InflowWind is a module for processing wind-inflow data generated in IECWind or TurbSim pre-processors. AeroDyn is a time-domain module that computes aerodynamic loads of horizontal axis wind turbines, and ServoDyn is a control and electrical drive model for blade pitch, generator torque, nacelle yaw, highspeed shaft brake and blade tip brake. A control system based on the DTU10MW controller has been tuned for the FLOTANT concept using the NREL's Reference OpenSource Controller (ROSCO) toolbox for wind turbine applications.

3.2. Design Load Cases (DLCs)

To check if the floating concept fulfils the requirements (Table 3) agreed by the consortia, a relevant subset of DLCs covering the global performance of the floater and the moorings behaviour was selected. The DLCs considered are presented in Table 4.

4. Floater

The FLOTANT platform is a concrete-plastic hybrid barge-type concept with a passive anti-flooding system (Figure 3). The floater is not watertight, and the floatability is ensured by filling the empty spaces within the floater using a low long-term water absorption extruded polystyrene material with a density of 0.95t/m³ [11].

The substructure contains a central concrete column linked to the external walls through concrete braces. The void space in between the braces is filled with the XPS foam material which is fixed to the bottom concrete slab by strands. The concrete tower provides the structural connection between the steel tower of the wind turbine with the bottom concrete slab. Six water ballast deposits are also fitted in the inner floater structure to help to compensate for the wind thrust. A heave plate is attached at the bottom of the floater to help with the heave motions control. The main dimensions of the floater are provided in Table 5 and depicted in Figure 3a.

Table 3 Motion and acceleration design criteria

DoF	Max	Mean	Standard Deviation	Max in Survival Condition	Mean in Survival Condition	Acceleration at the nacelle
Surge	± 30 m	-	-	-	-	2,94 m/s ²
Sway	± 30 m	-	-	-	-	
Heave	-	-	-	-	-	
Roll	$\pm 5^\circ$	$\pm 2,5^\circ$	1°	$\pm 7^\circ$	$\pm 5^\circ$	-
Pitch	$\pm 5^\circ$	$\pm 2,5^\circ$	1,5°	$\pm 7^\circ$	$\pm 5^\circ$	-
Yaw	$\pm 15^\circ$	-	-	-	-	-

Table 4 DLC list considered in the final loop of design

DLC	Comments	Wind/Sea state/Current model	Wind Speed [m/s]	Yaw error [°]	Wind/Wave misalignment [°]	Wave directions [°]	Number of simulations
1.2	Turbulence + normal sea state	NTM/NSS/ NCM	4to25@4	0	30; 0	0to60 @30	36
1.6	Turbulence + severe sea state	NTM/SSS/ NCM	9,4 / 11,4 / 13,4 / 25	8; 0	30; 0	-30to90 @30	160
2.3	Extreme gust + grid loss	EOG/NSS/ NCM	9,4 / 11,4 / 13,4 / 25	8; 0	0	30	24
2.4	Turbulence + grid loss	NTM/NSS/ NCM	4to25@4	0	0	30	6
2.6	One mooring line damaged	NTM/NSS/ NCM	9,4 / 11,4 / 13,4	-8	-30	30	18
2.8	Supply vessel impact, 2 ballast tanks flooded	NTM/NSS/ NCM	9,4 / 11,4 / 13,4	-8	-30	30	18
4.1	Normal wind conditions + normal sea state	NWP/NSS / NCM	4to25@4	0	0	30	18
6.1	Extreme wind and sea state	EWM/ESS /ECM	V50	8; 0	30; 0	-30to90 @30	40
6.3	Extreme wind and sea state + yaw misalignment	EWM/ESS /ECM	V1	20	30; 0	0to60 @30	36
6.4	Turbulence	NTM/NSS / NCM	1 / 3 / Va / Vb	0	30; 0	0to60 @30	24
7.1	Extreme wind and sea state + grid loss	EWM/ESS /ECM	V1	8; 0	30; 0	0to60 @30	24
7.3	One mooring line damaged	EWM/ESS /ECM	V1	-8	-30	30	6
7.5	Supply vessel impact, 2 ballast tanks flooded	EWM/ESS /ECM	V1	-8	-30	30	6

Table 5 Dimensions of the floater

Characteristics	Units	Values
Floater main diameter (D1)	m	48
Heave plate diameter (D2)	m	55.2
Concrete tower diameter (D3)	m	11.5
Concrete slab and heave plate height (H1)	m	2
Floater height (H2)	m	18
Concrete tower base height (H3)	m	16
Concrete tower top height (H4)	m	9
Draft	m	12
Displaced Volume	m ³	22028.85
Mass	t	21403.70

Figure 3 Floater (a) sketch and (b) inner structure

4.1. Ballast system

The ballast system features both active and passive water ballast. It comprises a set of six steel ballast tanks (1,218.86m³ each) filled with water (Figure 3b).

Part of the ballast water is considered as passive ballast (728 t) and therefore, it remains in its position regardless of the environmental conditions whereas another part of the ballast water, the active ballast (257.8 t), can be moved around the different ballast tanks to counteract the mean pitch and roll induced by the thrust of the wind turbine. Such a system can correct up to 11.8 degrees of mean rotation even though only 8.5 degrees are required. Therefore, further optimization of the system will be required.

4.2. Hydrodynamics and mooring lines

In this research, the FASTLink module is used to couple OpenFAST and OrcaFlex. When the FAST-OrcaFlex Interface [8] is used, all hydrodynamic and mooring loads are computed by OrcaFlex [9]. To use OrcaFlex, a hydrodynamic database (HDB) must be loaded in advance. OrcaWave is the tool selected to work out the HDBs employed during the project. Note that several different HDB must be set for the different conditions under analysis.

The mooring system designed for GC consists of four semi-taut lines using wire rope whereas for WoB a chain catenary system with five lines was developed (Table 6). The top view of the WoB setup is similar to the GC one (Figure 4) but presents three front lines instead of two, to be able to cope with the harsher environmental loads. All the lines in both locations are equipped with the innovative elastomer springs [11] shown in red in Figure 4. All mooring lines are attached to the bottom outside edge of the FLOTANT platform and fixed to the seabed by drag anchors in GC and gravity base caisson anchors in WoB. Fairlead and anchor positions are provided in Table 7.

Figure 4 mooring layout for GC site. Spring elastomers are marked in red.

Table 6 Mooring system parameters

Characteristic	Unit	GC	WoB
Wire (GC) and chain (WoB) outer diameter	mm	91.12	0.27
Mass density in air	kg/m	51.85	430
Axial stiffness	MN	525.00	1845
Seabed friction coefficient	-	0.50	0.50
Normal added mass coefficient	-	1.00	1.00
Normal drag coefficient	-	1.60	2.40
Axial drag coefficient	-	0.008	1.15
Unstretched length of frontlines	m	438.00	880.00/855.00/ 880.00
Unstretched length of backlines	m	361.14	952.00
Elastomer length	m	16	20

Table 7 Fairlead and anchor positions in meters from the centre of the floater and waterline

Site	Line	Fairlead x	Fairlead y	Fairlead z	Anchor x	Anchor y	Anchor z
GC	1	-27.6	0.00	-10.99	-383.18	-34.27	-250.00
	2	-27.6	00.00	-10.99	-383.18	34.27	-250.00
	3	13.8	-23.90	-10.99	155.94	-255.34	-250.00
	4	13.8	23.90	-10.99	155.94	255.34	-250.00
WoB	1	-27.6	00.00	-10.99	-847.01	0.00	-100.00
	2	-27.6	00.00	-10.99	-839.26	-233.90	-100.00
	3	-27.6	0.00	-10.99	-839.26	233.90	-100.00
	4	15.83	-22.61	-10.99	604.00	-738.76	-100.00
	5	15.83	22.61	-10.99	604.00	738.76	-100.00

4.3. Hydrodynamics: Panel pressures

The time-domain hydrodynamic pressure at the floater panels has been calculated since it is required for subsequent structural calculations. The hydrodynamic pressure calculated considers the sum of:

- Hydrostatic pressure around the hull
- Incident pressure from incoming waves
- Diffraction pressure due to interaction between waves and hull
- Radiation pressure due to waves created by the hull motion

4.4. Stability

This section presents the method and a summary of the results of the stability analysis. The analysis has been performed using the commercial software General HydroStatics (GHS). GHS is a code able to evaluate the flotation, trim, and stability of floating structures.

The stability analysis aims to assess the safety and performance of the FLOTANT concept against the design criteria detailed in [12] and considers the actions of static wind and hydrostatic forces in different system conditions. The study encompasses the assessment of the stability of the FLOTANT concept across the Pre-Service (construction), In-Service (production, survival, and open sea maintenance), and Non-Service conditions (transportation, installation, maintenance in protected sites and commissioning).

The FLOTANT concept fulfils the design criteria abovementioned in all the conditions studied. The In-Service conditions at WoB are the most challenging ones. Figure 5 depicts the righting arm and heeling arm curve graph for WoB considering 11.4m/s wind speed and headwind direction with ballast split equally between all tanks. This is the most challenging situation considered in the present analysis and comfortably passes the stability requirements demanding the area under the righting moment curve to the second intercept is equal to or greater than 140% of the area under the wind heeling moment curve. Subsequently, different analyses were performed considering only the required tank filled with the active ballast and different yaw misalignment angles. The platform fulfils stability requirements within a range of misalignment between -65° and 65° approximately (relative to the wind direction).

Figure 5 Righting arm and heeling arm curve graph WoB – 11.4m/s, headwind direction, ballast split equally between all tanks

Besides, the maximum Vertical Centre of Gravity (VCG) curves have been calculated showing the maximum possible overall VCG of the FLOTANT platform for a reasonable range of displacements shedding acceptable values.

4.5. Fatigue Limit State calculation

Fatigue resistance has been checked in two sections of the concept: the interface between the steel and concrete tower and the section of the concrete tower above the concrete tower braces. To calculate the Fatigue Limit State (FLS) of the abovementioned concrete elements, Markov matrices have been employed since the fatigue calculations for concrete require both, the mean stress value and the cycle stress range (local maximum and minimum) for each load cycle.

Markov matrices have been computed following the requirements stated in [13] considering DLCs 1.2, 2.4, 4.1, and 6.4 presented in Table 4 above.

5. Global performance results

This section presents a summary of the most relevant results from the analysis of the simulations of the integrated model of the FLOTANT concept.

5.1. Summary results

Table 8 presents a summary of the cases fulfilling the requirements presented in Table 3 considering the results of the simulations listed in Table 4 for the two locations under study.

Table 8 Percentage of cases satisfying the abovementioned requirements

	Surge (Max)	Sway (Max)	Roll (Max)	Roll (AVG)	Roll (SD)	Pitch (Max)	Pitch (AVG)	Pith (SD)	Yaw (Max)	Acc x (Max)	Acc y (Max)
%GC	100	100	94	98	60	95	98	92	100	100	100
%WoB	100	80	91	96	42	95	96	83	100	95	100

5.2. Load matrix

Table 9 presents the diagonals of the ultimate limit state load matrix obtained from the coupled simulations for GC and WoB sites for the tower base. The load matrix has been computed as required in [13].

Table 9 ULS load matrix

	F _x (kN)	F _y (kN)	F _z (kN)	F _{xy} (kN)	M _x (kN.m)	M _y (kN.m)	M _z (kN.m)	M _{xy} (kN.m)
Max GC	7746	7942	-17132	8096	410670	650160	33318	688743
Min GC	-4123	-4852	-25596	804	-663120	-335340	-41499	28031
Max WoB	10391	11553	-11872	11556	651510	835920	45698	777455
Min WoB	-9060	-8073	-30686	2024	-919620	-733050	-45144	194402

5.3. Panel pressures

Figure 6 below depicts the result of the panel pressures calculated for an instant of time within DLC 1.6.

Figure 6 Panel pressures calculated for DLC 1.6.

5.4. Fatigue loads: Markov matrix

Figure 7 below depicts a representation of the Markov matrix calculated for DLC 1.2.

Figure 7 Markov matrix for DLC1.2.

6. Conclusions and recommendations

The INS12MW GWT has been set up and presented along with the main characteristics of the FLOTANT floater and the mooring system optimized for deep waters.

The FLOTANT concept behaves satisfactorily from a general point of view presenting both low motions in the floater and low accelerations in the nacelle. The percentage of DLCs passing the restrictive criteria imposed by the FLOTANT consortia is adequate to the development stage of the concept. There is a remarkable trend increasing the percentage of cases fulfilling the criteria when compared with the first iteration design loop [1]. However, as presented in the summary of results, a few DLCs do not meet the criteria and therefore more in-deep analysis is required:

- The main reason behind many of the cases not fulfilling the requirements is the lack of requirements definition for certain conditions which have been encompassed within ‘Survival’ and required specific requirement definition e.g., line loss and supply vessel impact. These DLCs should have specific requirements since survival requirements are aligned to the desired response under extreme conditions rather than the desired response in accidental conditions.
- Beyond that, the mooring design is not stiff enough in the sway direction. A less directional mooring layout is suggested for the next optimization loop.
- Especially in the GC site, the dynamic behaviour is slightly poorer than the one presented in the first iteration design loop [1]. Therefore, it should be concluded that the previous catenary system suits better the FLOTANT concept than the current semi-taut configuration.
- Including buoys and weights into the mooring layout will help to achieve rotational motion improvements.

An example of load matrix, instantaneous panel pressures calculation result, and a Markov matrix worked out with the results of the DLC1.2 have been presented to show the kind of results needed to perform the subsequent structural analysis [3].

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References

- [1] Serret J, Kahn B, Cavanagh B, Lorente P, Pascal R, Girandier C, Cortes C, Duran R, McEvoy P and Castro A 2021. First Iteration Design of the Flotant Concept. *Proceedings of the ASME 2021 40th International Conference on Ocean, Offshore and Arctic Engineering*, OMAE2021
- [2] FLOTANT 2019. *Innovative, Low Cost, Low Weight And Safe Floating Wind Technology Optimized For Deep Water Wind Sites*.
- [3] FLOTANT 2020. *D4.1 – Structural And Naval Architecture Design Basis*.
- [4] Bak C, Zahle F, Bitsche R, Kim T, Yde A, Henriksen L C, Hansen M.H, Blasques J, Gaunaa M and Natarajan A 2013. *The DTU 10-MW Reference Wind Turbine*.
- [5] FLOTANT 2019. *D4.2 - Design Brief: Specifications of a generic wind turbine*.
- [6] Jonkman J and Buhl M 2005. FAST user's guide. Golden, Co.
- [7] IEC 61400-3 2009. *Wind turbines - Design requirements for offshore wind turbines*. Geneva.
- [8] NREL NWTC Information Portal (FAST-OrcaFlex Interface) 2011. Golden, Co.
- [9] ORCINA n.d. *OrcaFlex for offshore wind*. Technical Notes. Ulverston, UK.
- [10] FLOTANT 2020. *D2.1 – Mooring and Anchoring System Design*.
- [11] FLOTANT 2019. *D4.4 – Floater Predesign*
- [12] DNVGL-ST-0119 2018. *Floating wind turbine structures*. Oslo.
- [13] DNVGL-ST-0437 2016. *Loads and site conditions for wind turbines*. Oslo.